

Supply of Resources and their Management in Hittite Anatolia (SoRMHA) PRIN 2022 PNRR

https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/viewer?mid=1MFG4cUOiV_fogt7N9Ln8VR8z_NYsGSQ&ll=0%2C0&z=6

The link and the SoRMHA project details are also available at:

<https://www.anatolica.unifi.it/vp-219-supply-of-resources-and-their-management-in-hittite-anatolia-sormha.html>

